

Using Particle Filter for Estimating Velocity of Maneuvering Target Being Tracked by Passive Radar

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ABSTRACT

Tracking a target is achieved by estimating its range and velocity, and this process has two types: Bistatic Tracking and Cartesian Tracking. In a passive radar system, the bistatic tracking is achieved by processing the bistatic geometry “One non-cooperative transmitter and one receiver” for estimating the bistatic range and velocity. Whereas the Cartesian tracking is achieved by processing the bistatic geometry “Multiple non-cooperative transmitters or multiple receivers” for estimating the Cartesian range and velocity. Processing the bistatic geometry (Multiple non-cooperative transmitters or multiple receivers) has the following disadvantages: Extra signal processing and a ghost target phenomenon, compared with processing the bistatic geometry (One TX and One RX). In this paper, we propose a method for estimating only the Cartesian velocity of a maneuvering target, by using a particle filter with a passive radar that has the bistatic geometry “One (Digital Video Broadcasting-Terrestrial (DVB-T)) transmitter and one receiver”. This process is achieved by using two consecutive particle filters, whereas we depend on this filter as an estimation tool because of its efficiency, compared with other estimation tools. The first filter estimates the parameters of the target’s echo signal (i.e., Amplitude, Phase, Doppler Frequency, and Time delay), and the second filter estimates the target’s velocity depending on the outputs of the first filter (i.e., Doppler Frequency and Time Delay). The theoretical analysis of the proposed method is presented, and its efficiency is verified by simulating the mentioned passive radar and comparing the simulation results with the results of other researches.

Keywords: Passive Radar, Maneuvering Target, Particle Filter, Velocity Estimation.

المخلص

تجري عملية ملاحقة الهدف من خلال تقدير كل من مداه وسرعته، ويجري تقسيم عملية الملاحقة إلى نوعين: الملاحقة ثنائية الموقع والملاحقة الديكارتيّة. ومن أجل نظام الرادار السلبي، فإنّه يجري تحقيق الملاحقة ثنائية الموقع من خلال معالجة الهندسة ثنائية الموقع المكونة من مرسل غير متعاون ومستقبل وحيد، وذلك بغرض تقدير كل من السرعة والمدى ثنائيي الموقع. في حين أنّه يجري تحقيق الملاحقة الديكارتيّة اعتماداً على معالجة الهندسة ثنائية الموقع المكونة من مرسلاتٍ عدّة غير متعاونة أو مستقبلاتٍ عدّة، وذلك بغرض تقدير كل من المدى والسرعة الديكارتيين. تعاني معالجة الهندسة ثنائية الموقع مُتعدّدة المرسلات غير المتعاونة أو المستقبلات السيئات

التالية: معالجة إشارة إضافية وظاهرة الهدف الشبح، وذلك مقارنةً مع معالجة الهندسة ثنائية الموقع المكونة من مرسل غير متعاون ومستقبل وحيد. سنقوم من خلال هذه المقالة باقتراح نمط لتقدير السرعة الديكارتية لهدف مناوِر، وذلك من خلال استخدام المرشح الجزيئي مع الرادار السلبي الذي يمتلك الهندسة ثنائية الموقع المكونة من مرسل غير متعاون (من نوع إشارة البث الفيديو الرقمية-الأرضي (DVB-T) ومستقبل وحيد). يجري تحقيق هذه الإجرائية باستخدام مُرشحين جزيئيين متتاليين، إذ إنّه قد جرى الاعتماد على هذا المرشح كأداة للتقدير بسبب فعاليته مقارنةً مع أدوات التقدير الأخرى. يقوم المرشح الأول بتقدير معاملات إشارة صدى الهدف المتمثلة بالمطال، والطور، وتردد دوبلر، والتأخير الزمني، في حين يقوم المرشح الثاني بتقدير سرعة الهدف اعتماداً على المعاملات المقدّرة في خرج المرشح الأول (تردد دوبلر والتأخير الزمني). جرى تقديم التحليل النظري للنمط المقترح، وجرى إثبات كفاءته من خلال محاكاة الرادار السلبي المشار له آنفاً، ومقارنة نتائج المحاكاة مع نتائج أبحاث أخرى.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الرادار السلبي، هدف مناوِر، المرشح الجزيئي، تقدير السرعة.

INTRODUCTION

Passive radar is inherently a bistatic radar without having dedicated transmitters. It detects and tracks targets by processing reflections from commercial broadcast and communications signals, called non-cooperative transmitters, such as Frequency Modulation (FM) radio, Generations of Mobile Communication (Global System for Mobile communication "GSM" and Long-Term Evolution "LTE"), Digital Video Broadcasting-Terrestrial (DVB-T), Digital Audio Broadcasting (DAB), and Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) [1]. It is used in the surveillance of air, ocean, ground, and smart cities [2]. It has many advantages over active radar, such as resistance to jamming, lower cost, and no need for transmission hardware [1, 2]. Since this radar does not have dedicated transmitters, there is an additional signal processing represented by the implementation of a matched filter, which depends on a transmitted signal and is used for completing the detection of a target's echo signal. Therefore, the passive radar should receive a reference signal for creating the impulse response of the matched filter [1, 2]. Thus, it is equipped with two antennas for receiving two channels: The first channel is the surveillance channel that contains targets' echoes and multipath signals, and the second channel is the reference channel that contains only the reference signal. Many researches have been conducted studying this radar, such as: 1) Studying and analysing signals of non-cooperative transmitters (e.g., FM, GSM, DVB-T,

DAB, & GNSS), and determining the best signal for it [3-5]. 2) Studying the interference of the reference signal on the surveillance channel [6, 7]. 3) Detecting and tracking "maneuvering/non-maneuvering" targets [8-10]. The detection process is expressed as follows: Receiving the signals of radar's channels, reconstructing the reference signal, suppressing the interference in the surveillance channel, "Range-Doppler" Cross-correlation, and calculating the threshold detection [1, 2, 9]. Whereas the tracking process is expressed as estimating the targets' parameters (e.g., Bistatic and Cartesian Range, Time Delay, Doppler Frequency, Bistatic and Cartesian Velocity, Coordinates, Acceleration, and Direction of Arrival (DOA)) [11-24]. 4) Improving its structure by implementing the detection process without using the reference antenna [25, 26]. In this paper, we focus on the estimation of the parameter (target's velocity), which is classified as bistatic velocity or Cartesian velocity. For an illustration of this parameter, see Fig. 1, which represents the simple bistatic geometry of a passive radar. where TX is the non-cooperative transmitter, RX is the receiver with two receiving antennas, T_a is the observed target, SC is the Surveillance Channel, RC is the Reference Channel, R_1 is the range between the transmitter (TX) and the target (T_a), τ_1 is the time delay that corresponds to the range (R_1), R_2 is the effective range "or the Cartesian range", τ_2 is the time delay that corresponds to the range (R_2), D is the distance between the transmitter (TX) and the receiver (RX) "or the bistatic baseline", τ_D is

the time delay that corresponds to the distance (D) “or the direct path delay”, R_b is the bistatic range, τ_b is the bistatic time delay, (x_a, y_a, z_a) are the Cartesian coordinates of the target (T_a), V is the modulus of the target’s velocity vector “or the Cartesian velocity”, β is the bistatic angle, “or the angle between the line of sight (LOS) from the transmitter to the target, and the (LOS) from the receiver to the target measured at the target”, and δ is the orientation of (V) with respect to the bisector of the bistatic angle (β)^[1].

Fig. 1. Simple bistatic geometry of a passive radar.

The Cartesian velocity is the required parameter compared with the bistatic velocity because it represents the correct state of the observed target. The Cartesian velocity (V) is the resultant of the Cartesian components of the velocity vector (v_x, v_y, v_z) , or it is an actual velocity of an observed target. As for the bistatic velocity (V_{bis}), it is the Cartesian velocity in the bistatic geometry “Non-cooperative transmitter – Receiver” represented by an ellipsoid with foci at the location of the transmitter (TX) and the receiver (RX), or it is a velocity resulting from the processing of the bistatic Doppler frequency^[4, 27]. The bistatic velocity depends on the following parameters: Carrier Wavelength (λ), Bistatic Doppler Frequency (f_{dbis}), (δ), and (β), whereas it is given in Equation (1),^[1, 27]

$$V_{bis} = V \cos(\delta) \cos\left(\frac{\beta}{2}\right) = \frac{f_{dbis} \lambda}{2} \quad (1)$$

The bistatic velocity can be estimated by estimating the Doppler frequency (f_{dbis}) at the output of a bank of matched filters, whereas they are tuned to different Doppler frequencies. Therefore, it is estimated by using the simple bistatic geometry “One non-cooperative transmitter and one

receiver”. This process is called “Bistatic Tracking”, which is performed in the bistatic space (Range-Velocity) or (Time Delay-Doppler Frequency)^[1, 13, 23]. As for the Cartesian velocity, it is estimated by estimating the Cartesian components of the target’s velocity considering the bistatic geometry “Multiple non-cooperative transmitters or Multiple receivers”^[1]. This process is called “Cartesian Tracking” and is illustrated as follows: For estimating the Cartesian velocity of the observed target, we should estimate its coordinates, and for estimating these coordinates, we should estimate the parameter (τ_2) separately from the parameter (τ_1) at the output of the tuned matched filter. The parameters that can be estimated at the output of the matched filter (in the case of “One TX - One RX”) are (Doppler Frequency and Time Delay), whereas the parameter (Time Delay) is the bistatic time delay resulting from $(\tau_1 + \tau_2)$, so there is an ambiguity in the estimation of the target’s coordinates or its Cartesian velocity, and this ambiguity is reduced by using the multiplicity of non-cooperative transmitters or receivers^[1, 13]. The multiplicity of non-cooperative transmitters leads to an additional signal processing represented by designing the receiver and needing to save the transmitters’ positions relative to the position of the radar’s receiver, whereas the multiplicity of receivers leads to complex hardware and the possibility of detecting the radar’s position through the microwave connections between the receivers. In this paper, we propose a method for estimating the Cartesian velocity of a maneuvering target by using a particle filter with passive radar that has the bistatic geometry “One non-cooperative transmitter and one receiver (i.e., without using the mentioned multiplicity). It depends on the use of two consecutive estimation filters for estimating and analyzing the time delay and Doppler frequency of the target’s echo signal. For verifying the effectiveness of the proposed method in the case of a maneuvering target (which moves non-linearly during small time periods in the domain (Velocity-Direction)^[12, 27]), we suppose that the velocity of the observed target changes in a non-linear way, so we should use non-linear tracking filters, such as Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF), and Particle Filter (PF)^[12, 27]. Many researchers have indicated that the particle filter has the best performance for estimating non-

linearly changing parameters at a low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), so the particle filter is selected in the paper [12, 27].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, we present the following ideas: 1) The passive radar system with the proposed method. 2) The main principles of the particle filter, which is used for completing the method.

Passive Radar System

Bistatic Geometry

It consists of the geometry “One non-cooperative Transmitter and one Receiver”, whereas the transmitter is a DVB-T transmitter. This transmitter is selected because the (DVB-T) signal has the following advantages: First, it is a digital signal, so the reference signal can be perfectly reconstructed. Second, it has a small monostatic range resolution (approximately 20 (m)). Finally, it is robust to multipath fading because of its specifications. Depending on these advantages, many researchers have indicated that the DVB-T transmitter is the best transmitter for the applications of passive radar [1, 22].

Proposed Method

It depends on estimating the parameters of the target’s echo signal consisting of (Amplitude (A), Phase (φ) produced by the Doppler frequency (f_d), and Time Delay (τ)), and then estimating the Cartesian components of the target’s velocity depending on the estimated parameters (f_d & τ). The target’s echo signal, Doppler frequency, and time delay are given in Equations (2), (3), and (4), respectively [27, 28].

$$y(t) = A(t) e^{j\varphi(t)} S(t - \tau(t)) + n(t); \quad t = 0: T_p \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{d_t} &= \frac{-1}{\lambda} V_a(t) \left(\frac{X_a(t) - X_{TX}}{\|X_a(t) - X_{TX}\|} + \frac{X_a(t) - X_{RX}}{\|X_a(t) - X_{RX}\|} \right) \\ &= \frac{-1}{\lambda} \left(\frac{v_{x_t}(x_{a_t} - x_T) + v_{y_t}(y_{a_t} - y_T) + v_{z_t}(z_{a_t} - z_T)}{\sqrt{(x_{a_t} - x_T)^2 + (y_{a_t} - y_T)^2 + (z_{a_t} - z_T)^2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{v_{x_t}(x_{a_t} - x_R) + v_{y_t}(y_{a_t} - y_R) + v_{z_t}(z_{a_t} - z_R)}{\sqrt{(x_{a_t} - x_R)^2 + (y_{a_t} - y_R)^2 + (z_{a_t} - z_R)^2}} \right) \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_t &= \tau_{1t} + \tau_{2t} \\ &= \left[\sqrt{(x_{a_t} - x_T)^2 + (y_{a_t} - y_T)^2 + (z_{a_t} - z_T)^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \sqrt{(x_{a_t} - x_R)^2 + (y_{a_t} - y_R)^2 + (z_{a_t} - z_R)^2} \right] / c \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where t is the observation time, y is the echo signal of the observed target (or the observation signal), $S(t - \tau)$ is the delayed reference signal with the time delay (τ), n is the Gaussian noise of the observation process, T_p is the duration of the processed data window, λ is the carrier wavelength, V_a is the target’s velocity vector ($V_a = V$), (X_a, X_{TX}, X_{RX}) are the position vectors of the target, transmitter, and receiver, respectively, $\| \cdot \|$ is the Euclidean norm, (x_T, y_T, z_T) & (x_R, y_R, z_R) are the transmitter and receiver coordinates, respectively, (v_x, v_y, v_z) are the Cartesian components of the target’s velocity, and c is the speed of light in vacuum. By focusing on Equations (3) and (4), we can notice that the time delay is related to the target’s coordinates, and the Doppler frequency is related to these coordinates and the Cartesian components of the target’s velocity. Therefore, estimating the time delay and Doppler frequency will lead to estimate the following parameters: First, the target’s coordinates with an ambiguity related to the main summation in Equation (4) (e.g., in the case of normalized numbers, we can write $2\tau_1 + 2\tau_2 = 4\tau$, and $1.5\tau_1 + 2.5\tau_2 = 4\tau$ too). Second, the velocity components. Finally, the target’s velocity, which is estimated by calculating the resultant of the estimated velocity components. Therefore, the proposed method includes the following two estimation stages: The first stage is used for estimating the parameters of the target’s echo signal and determining the estimated Doppler frequency and time delay. The second stage is used for estimating the target’s velocity depending on the determined parameters from the first stage. Taking into consideration that the estimation tool in these two stages is the particle filter, which will be explained in the following subsection. We will depend on the type (Maximum Likelihood Particle Filter (MLPF)), which has less complexity with higher estimation accuracy compared with other types, such as Dirac Particle Filter (DPF) and Minimum Variance Particle Filter [12, 27]. The type (MLPF) depends on the maximum likelihood method and considers that each propagated particle represents (EKF). Figure 2 shows the flowchart of the proposed method, whereas we show only the estimated velocity for the following reasons: First, the coordinates are estimated with an ambiguity. Second, the parameter (f_d) is related to the resultant of the

velocity components. Finally, the parameter (velocity) is one of the main tracking parameters.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the proposed method.

Particle Filter

It is a non-linear filtering method used for solving estimation problems, and it was popularized in the early 1991-1993s [30, 31]. It depends on Monte Carlo approximation and recursive Bayesian estimation. In short, at each observation time, it is achieved by propagating, in a non-linear way, weighted particles in the domain of a studied state. The particles' weights and states are updated for getting estimation results, and then the propagated particles should be re-propagated in another domain based on the particles that have the highest weights using the resampling method [27-31]. For illustrating the relation between the proposed method and the particle filter, we should present the equations of the particle filter in the main case, and then in the case of the proposed method. In the main case, the particle filter processes two equations, the state equation, and the measurement equation, which are given in Equations (5) and (6), respectively, where t is the current measurement time, $(t - 1)$ is the previous measurement time, x is the state vector ($x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$), f is a nonlinear function and it is a known function

(State Function), w is the state's noise vector that has white Gaussian distribution ($w \in \mathbb{R}^{n_w}$); $w \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2 I)$, σ^2 is the variance, I is the identity matrix, Z is the measurement signal, and h is a nonlinear function and it is a known function (Measurement Function). The symbol $(\mathcal{N}(\mu, C))$ denotes the Multivariate Gaussian density function with the mean vector (μ) and the covariance matrix (C) [28, 29].

$$x_t = f(x_{t-1}) + w_t \quad (5)$$

$$Z_t = h(x_t) \quad (6)$$

These two equations will be expressed in the estimation stages of the proposed method, which contain two consecutive particle filters, as presented in the following subsection. Taking into consideration that the symbol (y) denotes the observation signal (Physical Signal), and the symbol (Z) denotes the measurement signal (Calculated Signal).

Equations of Two Particle Filters

Equations of the First Particle Filter

State Equation

It consists of the parameters related to the target's echo signal. It is given in Equation (7), where x_1 is the state vector of the first particle filter, i_1 is the index of the filter's particles; ($i_1 = 1: N_{s_1}$), N_{s_1} is the number of the filter's particles, ($w^A, w^\phi, w^{f_d}, w^\tau$) are the white Gaussian noises with zero means and different variances related to previous researches, and f_0 is the carrier frequency [12, 27, 28].

$$x_{1_t}^{i_1} = f_1(x_{1_{t-1}}^{i_1}) + w_t \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_t^{i_1} \\ \phi_t^{i_1} \\ f_{d_t}^{i_1} \\ \tau_t^{i_1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{t-1}^{i_1} \\ \phi_{t-1}^{i_1} + 2\pi f_{d_{t-1}}^{i_1} T_p \\ f_{d_{t-1}}^{i_1} \\ \tau_{t-1}^{i_1} - \frac{f_{d_{t-1}}^{i_1}}{f_0} T_p \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} w_t^A \\ w_t^\phi \\ w_t^{f_d} \\ w_t^\tau \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

We have mentioned that each particle represents (EKF), so we should present the Jacobian matrix (F_{s_1}) of the function (f_1) for completing the method of this filter, as given in Equation (8), [12, 27, 28].

$$F_{s_1}^{i_1} = \frac{\partial f_1(x_{s_1 t-1}^{i_1})}{\partial x_{s_1}} \Bigg|_{x_{s_1} = x_{s_1 t-1}^{i_1}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_A}{\partial A_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_A}{\partial \varphi_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_A}{\partial f_{d_{t-1}}} & \frac{\partial f_A}{\partial \tau_{t-1}} \\ \frac{\partial f_\varphi}{\partial A_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_\varphi}{\partial \varphi_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_\varphi}{\partial f_{d_{t-1}}} & \frac{\partial f_\varphi}{\partial \tau_{t-1}} \\ \frac{\partial f_{f_d}}{\partial A_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_{f_d}}{\partial \varphi_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_{f_d}}{\partial f_{d_{t-1}}} & \frac{\partial f_{f_d}}{\partial \tau_{t-1}} \\ \frac{\partial f_\tau}{\partial A_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_\tau}{\partial \varphi_{t-1}} & \frac{\partial f_\tau}{\partial f_{d_{t-1}}} & \frac{\partial f_\tau}{\partial \tau_{t-1}} \end{bmatrix}_{(i_1)} \quad (8)$$

Measurement Equation

It depends on substituting the particles' states in the measurement function (h_1), as given in Equation (9).

$$Z_{s_1 t}^{i_1} = h_1(x_{s_1 t}^{i_1}) = A_t^{i_1} e^{j\varphi_t^{i_1}} S(t - \tau_t^{i_1}) \quad (9)$$

The Jacobian matrix of the measurement function (h_1) is given in Equation (10), [12, 27, 28].

$$H_{s_1 t}^{i_1} = \frac{\partial h_1(x_{s_1 t}^{i_1})}{\partial x_{s_1}} \Bigg|_{x_{s_1} = x_{s_1 t}^{i_1}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial A_t} & \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \varphi_t} & \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial f_{d_t}} & \frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \tau_t} \end{bmatrix}_{(i_1)} \quad (10)$$

Equations of the Second Particle Filter

State Equation

It consists of the parameters related to the target movement in Cartesian space, as given in Equation (11), where x_{s_2} is the state vector of the second particle filter, i_2 is the index of the filter's particles; ($i_2 = 1:N_{s_2}$), N_{s_2} is the number of the filter's particles, ($\varepsilon x_a, \varepsilon y_a, \varepsilon z_a$) & ($\varepsilon v_x, \varepsilon v_y, \varepsilon v_z$) are the Gaussian noises with zero means and different variances. Taking into consideration that the main parameters are the velocity components of the observed target, not its coordinates. However, the coordinates should be added because they are used

for describing the movement of the observed target in terms of the coordinates that correspond to (τ).

$$x_{s_2 t}^{i_2} = f_2(x_{s_2 t-1}^{i_2}) + \varepsilon_t \Leftrightarrow$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{a_t}^{i_2} \\ y_{a_t}^{i_2} \\ z_{a_t}^{i_2} \\ v_{x_t}^{i_2} \\ v_{y_t}^{i_2} \\ v_{z_t}^{i_2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{a_{t-1}}^{i_2} + v_{x_{t-1}}^{i_2} T_p \\ y_{a_{t-1}}^{i_2} + v_{y_{t-1}}^{i_2} T_p \\ z_{a_{t-1}}^{i_2} + v_{z_{t-1}}^{i_2} T_p \\ v_{x_{t-1}}^{i_2} \\ v_{y_{t-1}}^{i_2} \\ v_{z_{t-1}}^{i_2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon x_{a_t} \\ \varepsilon y_{a_t} \\ \varepsilon z_{a_t} \\ \varepsilon v_{x_t} \\ \varepsilon v_{y_t} \\ \varepsilon v_{z_t} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The Jacobian matrix (F_{s_2}) of the function (f_2) is given in Equation (12), whereas it is used for completing the method of the selected particle filter [27].

$$F_{s_2}^{i_2} = \frac{\partial f_2(x_{s_2 t-1}^{i_2})}{\partial x_{s_2}} \Bigg|_{x_{s_2} = x_{s_2 t-1}^{i_2}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & T_p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & T_p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & T_p \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Measurement Equation

It depends on substituting the particles' states in the measurement function (h_2), as given in Equation (13), [12, 27].

$$Z_{s_2 t}^{i_2} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{a_t}^{i_2} \\ \tau_t^{i_2} \end{bmatrix} = h_2(x_{s_2 t}^{i_2}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{\lambda} \left[\frac{V_{a_t}^{i_2} (X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{TX})}{\|X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{TX}\|} + \frac{V_{a_t}^{i_2} (X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{RX})}{\|X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{RX}\|} \right] \\ \frac{\|X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{TX}\| + \|X_{a_t}^{i_2} - X_{RX}\|}{c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The Jacobian matrix of the function (h_2) is given in Equation (14).

$$H_{s_{2t}}^{i_2} = \left. \frac{\partial h_2(x_{s_2}^{i_2})}{\partial x_{s_2}} \right|_{x_{s_2}=x_{s_{2t}}^{i_2}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial x_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial y_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial z_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial v_{x_t}} & \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial v_{y_t}} & \frac{\partial f_{d_t}}{\partial v_{z_t}} \\ \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial x_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial y_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial z_{a_t}} & \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial v_{x_t}} & \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial v_{y_t}} & \frac{\partial \tau_t}{\partial v_{z_t}} \end{bmatrix}_{(i_2)} \quad (14)$$

See Appendix (A), which contains the parameters of Equation (14). To further clarify the relation between the first particle filter and the second particle filter, and for reducing the ambiguity of the second particle filter, we show the following figure achieved at each observation time. Taking into

consideration that the particle filter has a high performance because it consists of several Kalman filters, whereas the Kalman filter is Gaussian Filter-type (IIR). Therefore, there is Infinite Processing Memory that leads to an estimation with a high performance [32, 33]. The symbol (IIR) denotes the Infinite Impulse Response.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the second particle filter.

Remark (1): The initial values of the second particle filter are gotten by one of the following ways: First, implementing the studied particle filter many times at the first observations. Second, depending on results of other researches. Finally, using a third particle filter. In this paper, we depend on the first way.

Remark (2): The estimated parameters ($\hat{x}_a, \hat{y}_a, \hat{z}_a$) are the coordinates that lead to the correct bistatic time delay, and they do not match the actual coordinates, therefore they are not considered, unless in the case of targets that move according to

a straight trajectory. As for the estimated parameters ($\hat{v}_x, \hat{v}_y, \hat{v}_z$), they slightly match the actual parameters, but their resultant matches the actual velocity with an estimation accuracy, because the Doppler frequency depends on the target's velocity vector (i.e., the velocity resultant), as given in Equation (3). Therefore, we show only the parameter "Velocity", not its components. After presenting the research materials and methods, we will verify the efficiency of the proposed method by

the simulation and discussing the simulation results, as introduced in the following sections.

RESULTS

The results are presented after simulating the passive radar system. They are as follows.

Initial Conditions of the Simulation

By using MATLAB software, we have simulated the proposed method with the passive radar system shown in Fig. 1. This simulation is achieved with the DVB-T transmitter that has the following parameters:

- Effective Radiated Power = 50 (KW), 8K-mode, 16 Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16QAM), Bandwidth = 8 (MHz), $f_0 = 506$ (MHz), Position = (0, 10, 0) (Km).

The receiver has two receiving antennas and the following parameters:

- Surveillance Antenna Gain = 22 (dB), Reference Antenna Gain = 2.15 (dB), $T_p = 2.2$ (ms), the

time difference between two consecutive measurements = 215.5 (ms), Position = (0, 0, 0) (Km).

The maneuvering target (the observed target) has a Monostatic Radar Cross Section (RCS) = 5 (m²), and its initial position is (7.5, 12.9, 2.4) (Km). We consider that the target moves according to the trajectory shown in Fig. 4, and its velocity changes according to Fig. 5. Therefore, the SNR of the target's echo signal changes according to the range [5.2 → 13.4](dB). The range of the parameter "Signal-to-Interference Ratio (SIR)" is [-67.4 → -59.2](dB), which is used for completing the detection of the target's echo signal in the surveillance channel.

Fig. 4. Trajectory of the observed target.

The initial parameters of the two consecutive particle filters are as follows: $N_{s_1} = 27$, $N_{s_2} = 300$, which are chosen depending on the number of the parameters of each filter [27, 29]. Before presenting the simulation results, we should introduce the following metrics of the simulation efficiency, which will be illustrated for a general parameter (p).

- 1) An estimation error (d) is calculated as the difference between real values and estimated values ($d_p = p - \hat{p}$), where p is the real

Fig. 5. Velocity of the observed target as a function of time.

parameter and \hat{p} is the estimated parameter [27].

- 2) Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is calculated as $\left(RMSE_p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M (p - \hat{p})^2} \right)$, [27].

- 3) An estimation accuracy (σ_{ES}) (Standard Deviation) is calculated as: $\left(\sigma_{ES} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (d_i - \mu)^2} \right)$, where (M) is the number of the observations, and (μ) is the

expected value (Mean) of the estimation errors [12, 27].

- 4) A trusted estimation domain describes a changing of estimated values of a studied parameter around real values, whereas it is calculated as $(\mp 3\sigma_{ES})$, [12].

Simulation Results

After performing the simulation of the passive radar system, we obtained the following results: At the

output of the first particle filter, we can show the estimated parameters of the target’s echo signal; the amplitude, Doppler frequency, and time delay, as shown in Fig. 6, Fig. 7, and Fig. 8, respectively, whereas the estimation accuracies are as follows:

$$\sigma_{ES}^A = 0.014 \text{ (normalized)}, \quad \sigma_{ES}^{f_d} = 3.9 \text{ (Hz)},$$

$$\sigma_{ES}^T = 0.0156 \text{ (normalized)}.$$

Fig. 6. Real and estimated amplitude as a function of time.

Fig. 7. Real and estimated Doppler frequency as a function of time.

Fig. 8. Real- and estimated-time delay as a function of time.

Fig. 9. Real and estimated velocity as a function of time.

Taking into consideration that the time delay is normalized to the value $(Duration\ of\ DVB - T\ Symbol/10)$. The target’s velocity is estimated by considering the estimated parameters (Doppler frequency and time delay) as observation signals for the second particle filter, as shown in Fig. 9,

whereas the estimation accuracy is $(\sigma_{ES}^V = 5.17 \text{ (m/s)})$.

Remark (3): To differentiate between the Cartesian velocity and the bistatic velocity, we will present the estimation of the bistatic velocity, whereas the estimation accuracy is $(\sigma_{ES}^{V_{bis}} = 1.17 \text{ (m/s)})$, as

shown in Fig. 10. Taking into consideration that the Cartesian velocity is more efficient than the bistatic velocity for estimating the correct state of the observed target, whereas the bistatic velocity is related to the Doppler frequency (as given in Equation (1)), and the Cartesian velocity is related to its components in Cartesian space.

Fig. 10. Real and estimated bistatic velocity.

DISCUSSION

By studying the simulation results, we can attain the following points:

- Estimating the target’s velocity based on the passive radar that has the bistatic geometry “One Non-cooperative Transmitter and One Receiver” decreases the signal processing and complexity that are related to the multiplicity of non-cooperative transmitters or receivers.
- The estimation accuracy of the target’s velocity is related to the estimation accuracies of the parameters of the target’s echo signal (i.e., the Doppler frequency and time delay). So improving the estimation accuracies of these parameters will enhance the estimation accuracy of the target’s velocity.
- Other researchers have verified the efficiency of their different methods by studying the Cramer-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB), which is an important metric for evaluating the estimation performance [13-16, 19-21]. In this paper, we do not use this metric because there are two consecutive estimation stages. But we will verify the efficiency of the proposed method by comparing the simulation results with the results of the other researches listed in Table 1, at convergent conditions, such as the bistatic geometry, type of the observed target, RMSE, and

CRLB. By comparing our results with the results of (Ref [13] “1TX-1RX” and Ref [17]), we can notice that the results of the paper are perfect in terms of the simple bistatic geometry and RMSE. Therefore, the efficiency of the proposed method is verified, taking into consideration that our results are improved by enhancing the estimation accuracies of the parameters of the target’s echo signal, so there is simple additional signal processing related to the parameters of the estimation filters. As for the results of the other researches, they are improved by increasing the pairs of (Non-cooperative Transmitter-Receiver), whereas this process leads to an additional signal processing and more hardware (more cost).

Remark (4): By focusing on Fig. 9, we can notice that the estimated velocity does not change around the mean (i.e., the real velocity). This is caused by the performance of the second particle filter, which estimates the target’s velocity by calculating the resultant of the estimated velocity components using one observation (i.e., one TX-one RX), not multiple observations related to that multiplicity (as studied in other researches). Thus, using one observation may lead to a blind estimation, and for verifying the efficiency of the proposed method against the blind estimation, we will achieve the method by using the extended Kalman filter instead of the particle filter, as shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Estimated Velocity by using PF and EKF.

By comparing the results of using “PF” with the results of using “EKF”, we can notice the following points:

- The “EKF” estimates the target’s velocity with the estimation accuracy (18.1 (m/s)). This result

approximates the result of Ref [13] with (1 TX - 1 RX), as listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison with the other Results				
Ref./ Used Method	Bistatic Geometry	Type of Observed Target	RMSE (m/s)	CRLB (m/s)
Ref [13] / EKF	1 TX – 1 RX	Non-Maneuvering	[7.5 → 18]	[1.7 → 2.6]
	3 TX – 1 RX To 6 TX – 1 RX	Non-Maneuvering	It approximates the (CRLB)	
Ref [14] / ML	2 TX – 3 RX	Non-Maneuvering	~[8.2 → 23.4] It is related to SNR	~[7.3 → 21.2]
Ref [15] / ML	2 TX – 2 RX To 4 TX – 4 RX	Non-Maneuvering	Not indicated	~[0.75 → 3.2]
Ref [16]	2 TX – 2 TX	Non-Maneuvering	Not indicated	~0.65
Ref [17] / BRV & MaRV Filters	Not indicated	Non-Maneuvering	The minimum range: ~[5 → 10]	Not studied
	Not indicated	Maneuvering	The minimum range: ~[9 → 35]	Not studied
Ref [18] / PF	3 TX – 1 RX	Maneuvering	[4.5 → 7] It depends on the receiver's position and has values of about 50 (m/s) when the receiver is mobile	Not studied
The paper	1 TX – 1 RX	Maneuvering	9.2	Not studied

- The efficiency of the proposed method is better in the case of “PF” than in the case of “EKF”. This is illustrated as follows: The “EKF” is a linearization process of a nonlinear system using “First Order Taylor Approximation”, and it completes the estimation by analyzing the Jacobian matrixes of the system’s states for each studied parameter [13,27]. As for the “PF”, it has the following processes: First, it depends on the Maximum Likelihood method and considers that each propagated particle is “EKF”. Second, it studies and analyses the change of its

functions to each required parameter [28, 29], as given in Equations (8), (10), (12), & (14). Therefore, the “PF” is more efficient than the “EKF” in (Gaussian/non-Gaussian) - (Linear/non-Linear) systems [27, 29].

Remark (5): The proposed method is implemented in the complicated case, which is expressed in the case of a maneuvering target that moves according to the indirect trajectory with the velocity changing very non-linearly. Therefore, the efficiency of the proposed method is verified by the following points: First, simulating the passive radar system. Second, comparing the simulation results with the results of the other researches. Finally, considering

the Remark (4) and comparing it with the results of Ref [13] "1TX-1RX", which depends on "EKF", as listed in Table 1.

Remark (6): It is possible to implement the proposed method in observing cars on highways and estimating their velocities, whereas the cars are not maneuvering targets, so it can be implemented effectively, taking into consideration the effect of low Doppler frequency. This is the simple application for the proposed method, whereas the most effective application is tracking maneuvering targets, such as warplanes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper, the Cartesian velocity of a maneuvering target has been estimated by proposing a method with passive radar that has the bistatic geometry "One non-cooperative transmitter and one receiver". The proposed method depends on estimating and analyzing the parameters of the target's echo signal by using two consecutive particle filters, whereas the first filter estimates the parameters (Doppler frequency and time delay), and the second filter estimates the target's velocity based on the outputs of the first filter. The effectiveness of the proposed method has been verified by simulating the passive radar system and comparing the simulation results with the results of other researches.

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